

Role of Social Media in Promoting International Business in Rural Communities

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Abstract

The Study examined the role of media promotion businesses in rural communities in to internationally. to achieve that an objective was formulated and complimented with research question as follows; To examine the role of social media in promoting businesses in Nigerian rural communities internationally and What is the role of social media in promoting businesses in Nigerian rural communities internationally? The method used in the study was descriptive research. Frequency and percentages were used to interpret findings with the help of SPSS version 20. The instrument for data collection was tested using Cronbach Alpha coefficient which shows the instrument is reliable as it gives 0.745 which is above the threshold of 0.6 level of significance. the findings revealed that 80% of the respondent agree that Social media help in improving the number of international business ventures in Nigerian rural communities and 73.4% of the respondent agree that Social media promotes more rural businesses to international business than traditional media

Keywords: social media. International businesses, rural communities and Nigeria

1.1 Introduction

In today's global shift from self-content national economies to an interdependent and integrated global economic system has connect the world all together. The media are now exerting considerable activities in various ways which entrepreneurs in rural communities can introduce their product to international market and other multinational corporation can contract with them in the provision of raw materials. the term media refer to the periodic creation of information and content and dissemination which are intended for reception by, and which could have a clear impact on a significant of the public. This could inter alia include print media and media disseminated over electronic communication networks. Business and people today are connected with the help of media (either Traditional or Social Media) due to the ease of communication and linkages between boundaries (Kastsiolodes and Hadjidakis 2007 cited by Ogbari, Ajagbe, Oke, and Ejimotor 2016). According to Otokiti (2007) as cited by Ogbari, Ajagbe, Oke, and Ejimotor (2016) international business is all commercial transactions between two or more countries. These transactions include sales, investment and transportation as today global competition affect business at all levels either rural or urban. Thus, businesses in rural communities has a competitive advantage of their nearness to cheaper raw materials, but the concerns always remain as to how those businesses with these unique opportunities in the Nigerian rural communities such as the local palm oil factory in the southern part of the country can be promoted, what role could media play in their promotion of participant in one or more of international engagement, this and many more issues posit concerns as to how businesses in rural communities go to international. Thus, it is on this note, this study is motivated.

1.2 Research Problem

International business is concerned with the issues of all business transactions involving two or more countries which are devised and carried out across borders to satisfy individuals and organizations. This befitting business opportunity has unique advantages for businesses in the Nigerian rural communities especially with the continues decline in trade barriers and the role played by media in promoting it has not been given concerned by many researchers in Nigeria. Media as an agent of promotional tools in generating more sales, investment opportunities, and growth; the role of media cannot be overemphasized in the promotion of international business in Nigerian rural communities. Therefore, this study is motivated by the scarcity of contextual research to examine the role of media in the promotion of international business in the rural communities in Nigeria.

1.3 Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study is to Examine the role social of media in the promotion of international business in the rural communities in Nigeria. However, the study has the following specific objectives:

- i. To determine how mass media enhancing international business to rural communities in Nigeria
- ii. To examine the role of social media in promoting businesses in Nigerian rural communities to internationally.

1.4 Question and Hypothesis

- i. How does mass media enhance international business for rural communities in Nigeria
- ii. What are role of social media in promoting businesses in Nigerian rural communities to internationally.

1.4.1 Hypothesis

H0: there is no positive and significance relationship between social media in promoting rural communities to internationally.

2. Literature Review

There are many studies or manuscript on media and it roles, on rural communities and on international business. Thus, this aim to review related and relevant scholarly notes on the subject matter.

A rural area can be defined as an area characterized by sparse population and where the manufacturing base is mostly weak due to poor development or the absolute unavailability of required infrastructure (Sibanda, Musingafi and Chikuza 2011). Information is the key to an effective market operation and thus media plays a critical role in all aspect of business most especially in rural areas, media (either traditional or social) creates an effective rich of information that enable economic actors to make informed decisions; provides rural businesses with channels through which they can reach existing and potential investors, customers and sponsors and partners at international level (Olming and MacFargahur 2008).

2.1 Role of Traditional Media in promoting international business in Rural Communities

Kaushik and Dev (2013) conducted a study on effective media for rural communication: A study of panipet area in India; base on exploratory cum descriptive research and data were collected from hundred respondent base on convenient sampling method. From the study 60% of the respondent preferred television rather than newspaper, radio and other means of communication and among print media newspapers are the most preferred media and also around 60% respondent are newspaper subscribers. In congruence, also Matos (2012) conducted an investigation on mass media and globalization notes that mass media is playing a key role in enhancing globalization (international business) and multiple flows of information through international news broadcasts and television programs.

2.2 Role of Social Media in promoting international business in Rural Communities

According to Sibanda, Musingafi and Chikudza (2011), information and communication technologies (ICT) have a potential for economic growth and social empowerment. They further argue that rural economies can benefit from Information Communication Technology (ICT) by focusing on social production, social consumption and social services. They believe that ICT applications can enhance poor people's opportunities by improving their access to markets. They further argued that ICT can empower the poor for its application expand the use of government services, and reduce risks by widening access to micro finance. It is, however, important to note that sustained development using rural informatics is possible only if ICT interventions are able to respond to the local needs and re-adjust as per the prevailing knowledge of the rural areas.

Abuhashesh (2014) conducted a study on the integration of social media in businesses in july 2014, hypothesizes that smaller businesses can achieve strategic advantage through the adoption of social media communication in the contemporary global business environment. In the same vein Ogbari, Ajagbe, Oke and

Ejimofo (2016) conducted a study on empirical perspective of social media and international entrepreneurship in Nigeria, which examines critically the extent to which social media have contributed to the international venturing of entrepreneurs in Nigeria. The findings show that social media tools assist the business relationship of entrepreneurs in a foreign country, and also advancement in global information communication technology affect international venturing positively.

3. Methodology

This study is based on descriptive research. A secondary data study has been done to find out how both traditional media and social media play a role in promoting international business in Nigerian rural communities. Information from journal article and website was taken to provide this information. Then a primary study was conducted on 30 respondents in Taraba state university to find out the role played by media in promoting international business. Frequency and percentages were used to interpret findings with the help of SPSS version 20.

4. Data Analysis Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.745	6

The instrument for data collection was tested using Cronbach Alpha coefficient which shows the instrument is reliable as it gives 0.745 which is above the threshold of 0.6 level of significance as shown above

Question 1:

Mass media is a key to enhancing international business for rural communities in Nigeria

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	2	6.7	6.7	6.7
Disagree	6	20.0	20.0	26.7
Agree	11	36.7	36.7	63.3
Strongly Agree	11	36.7	36.7	100.0
Total	30	100.0	100.0	

Source: fieldwork

From the above table 73.4% of the respondent agree that Mass media is a key to enhancing international business for rural communities in Nigeria as against 26.7% who disagree with the statement.

Question 2:

Social media promotes more rural businesses to international business than traditional media

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	4	13.3	13.3	13.3
Disagree	4	13.3	13.3	26.7
Agree	14	46.7	46.7	73.3
Strongly Agree	8	26.7	26.7	100.0
Total	30	100.0	100.0	

Source: fieldwork

From the above table 73.4% of the respondent agree that Social media promotes more rural businesses to international business than traditional media as against 26.6 who disagree with the statement.

4.1 Hypothesis Testing

Correlations

		MEDIA	INTERNATIONALBUSINESS
MEDIA	Pearson Correlation	1	.605**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	30	30
INTERNATIONALBUSINESS	Pearson Correlation	.605**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	30	30

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

A Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to examine whether there is a relationship between social Media and the promotion of international business in rural communities in Nigeria. The results revealed a significant and positive relationship ($r = .60$, $N = 30$, $p = .00$). The correlation was moderate in strength. Higher levels of media were associated with the promotion of international in rural communities in Nigeria.

4.2 Major Findings

The below are the major findings of the study

- i. 73.4% of the respondent disagree that Mass media is a key to enhancing international business for rural communities in Nigeria.
- ii. 80% of the respondent agrees that Social media help in improving the number of international business ventures in Nigerian rural communities.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

From the foregone analysis it will be concluded that there is significant relationship between the role social of media in the promotion of international business in the Nigerian rural communities. However, the following recommendation are worthy to be made:

- i. Rural community's entrepreneurs should use all platform to promote their businesses internationally in order to gain more market share.
- ii. Promoting rural businesses to international market should be encourage as it provides strategic advantage to the businesses.
- iii. Social media should be integrated with traditional media in the promotion of international business in rural communities in Nigeria.

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